

Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) annual cumulative report

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Year 1: September 15, 2021 - August 31, 2022

Accomplishments:

Major Project Goals:

The goal of Big-Bee is to expand bee research through the digitization of bee traits and images. To accomplish this goal, we will create over 1.2M images of over 5K bee species and share these images via the Bee Library and through published curated datasets. These goals will be accomplished using many methods, including the development of novel Notes from Nature measurement tools.

The digitization goals of Big-Bee are (Table 1):

1. 572,813 newly digitized specimens of 5,509 target taxa. The focus is on complete digitization, which includes georeferencing, and images with both specimen and labels.
2. ca. 109,000 high-resolution, multi-focal stacked Exemplar and Diagnostic images including focal taxa and bee parasites.
3. 10,300 3D Image Suites for 3D image reconstruction.
4. Score Morphological Traits from images including Body Size, Hair Color, and Hairiness.
5. Score Life History Traits from literature including Phenology, Nesting Biology, Sociality, and Biotic Associations Including Floral Specialization, Parasites, and Pathogens.

Data and images will be discoverable via iDigBio, GBIF, Bee Library (Symbiota database), and as published, curated datasets.

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
Arizona State University (ASUHC)	10,000	0	0	
California Academy of Sciences (CAS)	142,325	5,474	500	
Florida State Collection of Arthropods (FSCA)	90,495	5,294	500	
Harvard University (MCZ)	52,324	6,492	500	
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	2000	0	0	2,000 (microCT)
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM)	72,681	6,543	500	
San Diego Natural History Museum (SDMC)	14,224	797	3,000	
University of California-Berkeley (EMEC)	69,297	9,892	100	
University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB)	8,697	5,092	4,000	
University of Colorado (UCMC)	62,677	10,160	100	
University of Kansas (SEMC)	9,495	28,185	100	
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology (UMMZ)	27,815	15,198	500	

University of New Hampshire Collection of Insects and Arthropods (UNHC)	6,783	12850	500	1,000 (CLSM)
USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab (USGS BIML)	4000	4,000	0	
Total:	572,813	109,977	10,300	3,000

Table 1: Digitization goals outlining the 572K specimens to be published and digitized using multiple imaging modalities; 109K high-resolution, focal stacked exemplar and diagnostic images; 10,300 3D image suites consisting of ~64 focal stacked images per suite; and 3,000 CT or CLSM images. Grey highlighted rows are non-funded partners.

Biodiversity Informatics goals are:

1. Create the Bee Library as a Symbiota portal dedicated to bees and bee traits;
 - a. expand Symbiota’s ability to link to external resources, including the ability to link to: externally managed literature (via Weblink DOI), observations (e.g., iNaturalist), other image datasets (e.g., CT, CLSM, and 3D models held outside of ASU), and other related specimens;
 - b. investigate options for sharing Image View (e.g., dorsal, ventral) as a property in Audubon Core in Symbiota;
 - c. extend the Symbiota Trait Management Tools developed by the CAP TCN to manage bee traits from both literature and specimen sources;
 - d. extend the image and dataset search capabilities in Symbiota based on locality, taxon, and view; and
 - e. Add bee observation collections.
2. publish versioned datasets of the textual trait data and “training datasets” of image data as products;
3. establish connections between Bee-Bee Global Biotic Interactions, iDigBio, and GBIF;
4. investigate computer vision for traits and improved methods for 3D image reconstruction;
5. integrate additional bee data from network collections, monitoring programs, and federal collections (e.g., USGS, USDA, Smithsonian) via established IPTs or spreadsheet uploads; and
6. participate in the OpenTraits Network.

Outreach, workforce training, and broader impact goals:

1. Create a Research Advisory Board;
2. provide digitization resources for all global bee collections including the ability to digitize specimens through the Big-Bee Symbiota portal, and support from a portal data manager to help train and facilitate the upload and data sharing;
3. participate fully with the Bee Monitoring USDA-RCN;
4. create a science-themed radio program about bees;
5. contribute lesson plans to BLUE (Biodiversity Literacy for Undergraduate Education);
6. continue efforts to recruit students from underrepresented groups;
7. provide opportunities for all participants to advance skills in biodiversity information science, bee identification, high-resolution imaging, museum curation, and outreach.
 - a. 3D and high-resolution imaging provided by Mark Smith, owner and developer of Macroscopic Solutions, LLC;
 - b. data curation and workflows using Symbiota portal including georeferencing, data management, trait annotation, and Bee Library dataset creation;
 - c. annotating and defining traits in the Bee Library;
 - d. creating a citizen science bee inventory using the Bee Library to create identification tools.
 - e. online bee morphology and Bee Library workshops will be developed in years two and three of the project. The first will focus on bee male genitalia and it will include how to prepare specimens and use the Bee Library for identification by comparing images to dissected

specimens. In year three, a two-day virtual workshop on bee identification and trait determination will train novel bee researchers on how best to use the Bee Library to inform their identification efforts.

- f. two undergraduate computer science projects will be developed by a Postdoctoral Researcher at UCSB for incorporation into the recently funded NSF “HDR DSC: Collaborative Research: Central Coast Data Science Partnership: Training a New Generation of Data Scientists” initiative.

Accomplishments Under These Goals:

Started Project: All 13 institutions funded by the grant are engaged and successfully contributing to the project (UNHC, UMMZI, UCSB, FSCA, LACM, UNR, SEMC, SDMC, UCMC, CAS, EMEC, ASUHIC, MCZ - see participant list at end of document for institution details). All institutions have hired and trained the staff, technicians, or students working on the project.

Major Equipment and Macroscopic Solutions: 3D, Diagnostic and Exemplar images for this project rely on the Macropod PRO 3D & Micro Kit (<https://macroscopicsolutions.com/product/the-macropod-pro-3d>). All Macroscopic Solution Imaging systems and equipment updates were delivered. This includes new imaging systems delivered to 8 institutions and updates of existing imaging systems to 3 institutions. FSCA and UCR did not require systems or updates to existing systems.

The workflow Macroscopic Solutions created for Big-Bee is a 3-step method requiring the Macroscopic Solution Macropod Pro 3D imaging system, Zerene Stacker’s focus stacking software, and Agisoft Metashape’s photogrammetry software.

The Macropod Pro 3D uses a motorized linear stage and rotary stage that automatically moves the specimen relative to the camera, lens, and lighting apparatus. The specimen is photographed and illuminated from back to front using the linear stage to record thin and overlapping focal sections used to generate a final focus stacked image of the specimen. Images are captured using a speed light flash and open aperture to physically produce the sharpest image possible of each individual focal plane. This process is repeated as the rotary stage rotates the specimen around a vertical axis perpendicular to the lens in 2-degree intervals along two opposing 235-degree arcs. In this example, the process is repeated 235 times. (Example: <https://youtu.be/wznsRLOpSiw?t=612>)

Zerene Stacker discards blurry areas of each image and combines each focal section to create an output image that is completely in focus; hence the term, focus stacking. A folder splitter automatically separates pre-focus stacked images into 235 unique folders and a batch processor automatically focus stacks all 235 perspectives. The result is 235 high-resolution, color-accurate images captured concentrically around the specimen comprising the adequate dataset required for photogrammetry. (Example: <https://youtu.be/wznsRLOpSiw?t=695>)

Agisoft Metashape analyzes and aligns all 235 images and virtually places them into the exact position relative to the specimen from where they were captured. The methods used to align these photos can sometimes vary; however, subsequent steps remain the same. The software creates a 3D model by triangulating tie points identified from changing perspectives from adjacent source imagery. The color profiles from each source image are matched and combined to render the external texture resulting in a highly detailed volumetric model of any specimen >50 microns in size. (Example: <https://youtu.be/wznsRLOpSiw?t=1387>)

Big-Bee prompted five key and important innovations, two related to hardware and three related to workflow efficiency. Innovative solutions relating to hardware are designed to consistently illuminate specimens with minimal to no anomalies between shots (i.e., glare, reflection, oversaturation, poor contrast) and the option to easily orient specimens in a gimbal-like fashion to mount specimens quickly and efficiently. A light dome, translational camera riser, and flash arms were designed and outfitted to fix two light sources throughout the imaging process. The light dome is specifically designed to diffuse light from the source and reflect light onto every part of the specimen being imaged. The universal stage and translational camera riser offer 5-axes of motion to center and orient the specimen (i.e., x, y, z, a, and b) with ease and without compromising image quality. The light dome has a break away to easily access the universal stage providing an ergonomically accessible platform for the user.

Innovative solutions relating to workflow efficiency are designed to capture the fewest images possible using a refined auto-step method that captures the exact number of photos required according to the

corresponding aperture and magnification and a precise 2-degree interval between rotations along two opposing 235-degree arcs without requiring a second arc situated perpendicular to the first. This is made possible by the Universal Stage, which mounts pinned specimens obliquely instead of vertically to capture the top-side and under-side as the specimen rotates around a single axis. Traditional photogrammetry requires specimens be oriented vertically, which does not allow the camera/lens to capture the top-side and under-side of the specimen without requiring additional images around a second axis. This effectively reduces the total capture time by 50%. The universal stage also allows for specimens to be stacked along the short axis, which also reduces capture time by an additional 50%. Ongoing research and development aim to further reduce the required 2-degree interval to a 4-degree interval, reducing capture time by another 50%.

Software updates and improved AI will eventually increase workflow pace as software developments are released over time. Automatic masking and improved computer performance will increase photogrammetric alignment and will require smaller datasets in the future. For now, our collaboration with Big-Bee introduced a novel stereo reconstruction method that does not require a dense point cloud model prior to point triangulation. This method requires 2-3 coded tweaks in Agisoft, which was shared with all Big-Bee collaborators. (Example: <https://www.agisoft.com/index.php?id=48>)

Big-Bee provided Macroscopic Solutions with the opportunity to work more closely with Agisoft Metashape, a key software vendor providing photogrammetric 3D modeling capabilities. Macroscopic Solutions worked closely with Metashape engineers to shorten workflows using a novel stereo production method over the commonly used point cloud generation method. The stereo production method requires an initial alignment prior to constructing the model. The point cloud generation method requires an alignment and a dense point cloud to construct the model.

Big-Bee inspired a new product design for the innovative light dome and universal stage. CNC computing and hardware introduced Macroscopic Solutions to three new vendors providing the resources necessary for product design and production. These three vendors include two large businesses (Autodesk and Xometry) and one small business (PocektNC).

Digitization Workflows: The first 6 months of the project were focused on refining digitization workflows and developing many of the digitization and reporting workflows collaboratively, with significant input from MCZ, Essig, UCSB, SDMC, LACM, CAS, UCMC, ASU (Symbiota Support Hub), and Erika Tucker (Parasite Tracker). To standardize the **Label with Specimen Images workflows** (Figure 1), all institutions received one or more (32 in total) Essig-style custom imaging trays created by Dylan Valle Rogers for the project. These trays were designed by Peter Oboyski (Essig) and standardized scale bars were delivered by Seltmann (UCSB). Further file name standardization criteria were set by participants to tag or label images. These labels are translated into image views in the Bee Library. Standard view labels follow the MCZ labels.

Figure 1: Example of a Label with Specimen Image workstation and output image with a standardized ruler and imaging box from the CAS collection.

Digitization: 64,454 images have been captured for Big-Bee (September 15, 2021 - July 13, 2022)

Label with Specimen Image Digitization: Big-Bee will image, transcribe, and georeference **572,813** new specimens as part of the project. We have already completed approximately **10%** of our imaging goals (Figure 2; Table 2).

Figure 2: Label with Specimen digitization progress

	Complete	Remaining
Specimen Images	58,014	514,799
Transcribed	12,163	560,650
Georeferenced	11,296	561,517

Table 2: Label with Specimen digitization progress

Exemplar, Diagnostic and 3D Image Digitization: **4,300** Exemplar Images, **591** Diagnostic Images, and **12** 3D models were created so far for the project. **1441** multi-focal stacked images were generated to create the **12** 3D models, averaging **120** images per model. These images are multi-stacked images photographed with the Macropod Pro imaging system (Table 3).

	Complete	Remaining
Exemplar & Diagnostic Images	4,891	105,086
3D	12	10,288

Table 3: High-resolution imaging progress

If the trend continues, at ca. **120** images per 3D model, the resulting total images that Big-Bee will create for 3D reconstruction is **1,236,000**. This is almost double the previous estimate, which was **64** images for each model, resulting in **659,200** images.

Male Terminalia Imaging: One of the specialized diagnostic imaging suites in the Big-Bee project is male terminalia imaging. UNHC created **270** high-resolution brightfield images of the male terminalia of *Andrena* species (120 images of *Andrena* specimens from T. B. Mitchell's bee collection from NCSU) and collected **23**

CLSM 3D datasets (dorsal and ventral view). We have also collected an additional **108 3D images suites**. UNHC gathered 4 males for about 36 species and 4 females for 40 species of *Andrena* from Sophie Cardinal (CNCI) and 56 specimens representing numerous Andrenidae genera from the Florida Department of Agriculture (FDACS). Specimens from FDACS have been identified by experts and specimens from CNCI have been barcoded. After removing the abdomen tips, these specimens will be sent to the Karlsruhe Institute of technology for synchrotron-based micro CT (Thomas van de Kamp).

Digitization Progress Per Institution:

All Big-Bee digitizing institutions have begun digitization with significant progress just starting in the last quarter of this year. The details for each institution are detailed in Table 4.

	UNHC	UMMZI	UCSB	FSCA	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHC	MCZ
Label with Specimen Images	1000	7275	2585	8200	0	1369	5599	3928	9806	5539	1002	11711
New specimens data transcribed	0	0	2500	8796	0	180	0	0	0	687	0	0
New specimens georeferenced	0	0	2500	8796	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Focus-stacked Exemplar Images	118	0	114	610	318	33	101	564	920	0	1002	520
Focus-stacked Diagnostic Images	270	0	321	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Images for 3D image reconstruction	108	0	1441	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4: Digitization progress per Institution.

Notes from Nature: To facilitate label transcription, and to measure body size, UNR built a custom Notes from Nature project for Big-Bee called the Big-Bee Bonanza. The project includes a designated bee-themed landing page and several pages that outline information about how community scientists can get involved in the Big-Bee project. It also includes information about the research goals, project team members, a place to track project statistics, and a forum for online discussion. The Big-Bee Notes from Nature Project includes **3** custom workflows to suit the needs of researchers and ensure standardized data outputs. Two of these workflows are focused on transcription of label information. The third is for measuring bee tegula, a proxy for body size. Peter Oboyski (EMEC) worked with Michael Denslow (UNR) and PI Seltmann (UCSB) to create the content for the new project. Oboyski wrote the important FAQ section of the site and drew upon over 10 years experience in digitizing specimens using Notes from Nature for the Essig Museum. The new project was reviewed by participants and collaborators from LACM, UCSB, UCMC, EMEC, MZC, ASU, CAS, Robert Guralnick, and Erika Tucker prior to launch, demonstrating the highly collaborative nature of the Big-Bee project. At launch, the project was promoted via social media (i.e., Twitter, Facebook, Instagram), including the social media engine of CAS which has 271.9K followers on Twitter.

The UNR team has also customized a data processing algorithm to better suit the needs of the research team. The Big-Bee Bonanza project launched in July and already has over **2,000** completed subjects and **377** volunteers in the first 2 weeks. <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>.

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: The Big-Bee Symbiota portal (Bee Library - <https://library.big-bee.net>) was rapidly launched in the first quarter of the project (October 2021). The portal is managed by the newly established Symbiota Support Hub at ASU.

The bee library hosts **2,074,031** occurrence records from **17** specimen collections and **1** observation collection containing iNaturalist observations. **87%** of the specimens are georeferenced, **39%** contain images (818,200 images) and **50%** are identified to species (retrieved July 21, 2022). All Big-Bee participants are sharing data with the Bee Library.

Figure 3: Lateral whole body image search in the Bee Library is based on an image tagging system that incorporates both image view and subject in the search.

As part of this initial launch, a series of initial setup configurations were completed, including:

- Forked Symbiota code into a new Big-Bee Network GitHub organization/project: <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/Symbiota-light>
- Integrated the configuration styling components (graphics, header, footer, central page content, etc) into the Big-Bee code fork created by PI Seltmann and Andrew Johnson
- Used the Big-Bee code repository to install a Symbiota code instance on ASU Symbiota Support Hub server
- Built MariaDB (MySQL) database to serve as the central backend data source. Nightly MySQL data dumps serve are deposited on a remote serve storage system that will serve as regular database backups
- Established storage within an adjacent server mount that will serve to store and publish image and media files associated with the Big-Bee portal
- Configured server to use the Big-Bee data library domain name (library.big-bee.org) as the central URL
- Installed a LetsEncrypt SSL security certificate to provide data encryption
- Setup and configured Google Map API keys, Google Analytics, and Recaptcha spam protection
- Occurrence data mapping and loading
 - Seventeen Natural History Collection profiles were established within the portal with complete collection metadata and contact information. The majority of specimen records were imported from IPT data providers established and maintained by the source collections.
 - One iNaturalist observation dataset was established

Taxonomic Authority Support: A central taxonomic thesaurus was built using several taxonomic authoritative resources. The immediate focus of the taxonomic tree is on Apoidea. The taxonomy from Kingdom to Genus was imported via Catalog of Life (<https://www.catalogueoflife.org>), which follows the ITIS taxonomy for

Apoidea. Species, subgenera, and infraspecific taxa were imported via a data dump obtained from Discover Life.

Image Sharing: Working with ASU Hub Ed Gilbert & Andrew Johnston, Big-Bee defined the first set of image descriptive terms to use in searching the Bee Library for images. To do this, we adopted an abbreviated list based on the MZC list of standard imaging views. The views are incorporated in Symbiota Bee Library as a “Tag” that can be applied to images, resulting in a person's ability to retrieve all images of a specific bee view. The example pictured below (Figure 3) is the view of an image search with the lateral habitus filter applied to view images of the whole body from the lateral perspective.

Global Biotic Interactions: 134,802 biotic interactions are shared from Big-Bee institutions to Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) as of July 27, 2022. This is the first publication of a verifiable Image Corpus from the UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection using Preston, a biodiversity data tracker. This image corpus contains 14,349 images related to 32,533 occurrence/specimen records that can be independently stored, retrieved, and cited, regardless of where the images and their metadata happen to be stored. The image corpus was deposited at Zenodo and the Internet Archive and provides an example of how valuable image collections can be duplicated and distributed while guaranteeing the authenticity of both their content and provenance (or origin).

Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021). UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5660088>
hash://sha256/80c0f5fc598be1446d23c95141e87880c9e53773cb2e0b5b54cb57a8ea00b20c

Seltmann and Poelen collaborated to create a citable, and reusable, version of the existing and often used DiscoverLife bee catalog guide and world checklist. Discover Life bee checklist is considered the best reference for bee names in North America.

Seltmann, Katja, & Poelen, Jorrit. (2022). Tab and comma delimited versions of Discover Life bee species guide and world checklist (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila) (v55.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6147345>

Seltmann and Poelen established a data monitoring page at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee> to help review, and keep track of, the availability of Big-Bee associated natural history collections. The reviews link via shared IPT or Darwin Core archives and include an examination of taxon names, number of biotic interactions, and data structure

Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022). Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.2.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915003>

UCSB Seltmann Participated in TDWG Audubon Core Views Controlled Vocabularies Task Group (<https://github.com/tdwg/ac/blob/master/views/README.md>) utilizing Big-Bee images as a use case for the development of standard vocabulary for subject and specimen orientation to improve the searchability of images in NHC databases.

What opportunities for training and professional development has the project provided?

A weekly meeting via Zoom continues to be an important part of creating Big-Bee workflows, project organization, and onboarding new participants. The zoom meetings are very well attended by participants, Symbiota Support Hub staff, project consultants, Macropod Solutions staff, and other project collaborators. The meetings also provided a venue for imaging training by Mark Smith (Macroscopic Solutions). They have, and continue to, provide much-needed open office time for questions.

Big-Bee uses Slack software to enhance communication. We presently have **101** members on Slack including project PIs, collaborators, Symbiota Support Hub staff, undergraduates, and technicians. Slack is being used for day-to-day project management and training/communication about imaging, Notes from Nature, and other project goals.

MCZ shared progress in a weekly meeting with the Big-Bee group on the "BugFlow" workflow sharing platform on GitHub. Established standards across the Big-Bee collaborative for documenting workflow metadata for all workflows created as part of the grant will be deposited on BugFlow.

Pete Oboyski (EMEC) advised individuals from several other institutions on label imaging standards and workflows via the Entomology Collections Network listserv and via the Big-Bee weekly meetings. EMEC also launched a training exercise to teach digitization assistants about scientific names and the spatial organization of a natural history museum followed by a scavenger hunt to find species in a collection of over 40,000 species and 5.5 million specimens.

How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?

- A total of **3** student oral presentations, **5** student posters, **7** student research projects, and **1** published scholarly article.
- Big-Bee was mentioned in **20** academic presentations this year.
- Big-Bee was presented or discussed in **18 events** (i.e., open house, collection tours) across the network, with **4367 attendees**.
- There were **6 articles** about the project in newsletters, periodicals, or other non-scholarly venues.
- We developed a social media hashtag, #bigbee for all social media platforms.
- PI Seltmann is participating in the Bee Monitoring RCN project by co-developing a workshop for Spring 2023 on biodiversity informatics for the bee community.
- A poster about the project was included in the 2021 - 2022 TDWG, International Union for the Study of Social Insects (IUSSI), XII Congreso Mesoamericano de Abejas Nativas, Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas Tropicales (CINAT), Entomological Society of America (accepted) and Entomological Collection Network (planned).
- Rather than developing independent help resources, Big-Bee is committed to helping develop the Symbiota Support Hub (<https://symbiota.org/help-resources>) and Macroscopic Solutions help resources for the entire community.
- Macroscopic Solutions has created open-source PDFs and tutorial videos describing photogrammetric workflows. These videos are accessible on Macroscopic Solutions Youtube channel and website. Since creating this content, Macroscopic Solutions has seen a sharp increase in academic-based subscriptions. (Examples: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg> and <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn/>)
- Big-Bee is represented via our websites, GitHub project, and data portals (see Products). The Bee Library Symbiota portal was visited by **15,885** users since Google Analytics was installed on October 31, 2021. The average number of views per day was **4** between October 31, 2021 - June 3, 2022. The average between June 13, 2022 - July 28, 2022, is **105**. Most of the views are unique visitors, with only **32** users being repeat visitors.

What do you plan to do during the next reporting period to accomplish the goals?

- During the second year of the project, all Big-Bee institutions will focus on reaching their digitization goals, including 3D imaging.
- To facilitate workforce training and digitization, PI Seltmann and Mark Smith (Macropod Solutions) are developing an online 3D imaging short course to guide institutions in 3D imaging. This will also provide community workforce training.
- Seltmann and consultant Jorrit Poelen are developing a taxon name resolution half-day short course as part of the Big-Bee workforce training objectives.
- We will continue to improve our DEI survey in collaboration with iDigBio EODI for our next annual report.

- We will continue to work closely with our partners at the ASU Symbiota Support Hub to improve image and data searching in the Bee Library portal.
- We will continue Notes from Nature expeditions for both body size measurements and label transcriptions.
- Year 2 will focus on trait data, including how to incorporate trait data into the Bee Library Symbiota portal. UCSB postdoctoral researcher Madeline Ostwald will focus on aggregating trait data to include in the portal and as separately published datasets.
- Poelen and Seltmann will continue examining image corpus publication for image datasets, particularly around 3D image models.

Products

Published Conference Abstracts:

1. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 5: e74037. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.74037>

Talks/Posters:

1. Seltmann, KC. (2021) New TCN: Big-Bee. Virtual ADBC Summit. Presentation for iDigBio and the ADBC program. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/ADBC_Summit_2021 on 21 Sept 2021
2. Seltmann, K.; Allen, J.; Brown, B. V; Carper, A.; Engel, M. S; Franz, N., et al. (2021). Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 5(e74037). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0937b5gp>
3. Gonzalez, VH., Seltmann, KC., Brown, B., Allen, J., Carper, A., Engel, M., et al. (2021). Big-Bee: Una iniciativa para promover el conocimiento de las abejas a través de la digitalización de imágenes y datos de rasgos. ID 112. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0856h3d2>. Poster from XII Congreso Mesoamericano de Abejas Nativas, Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas Tropicales (CINAT), Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica, Nov. 20-21, 2021. The poster is in Spanish.
4. Eisner de Eisenhof, L., & Seltmann, K. (2022). Body Size and Taxonomic Influence on Bee Wing Vein Density. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0z73n6vt>
5. Xu, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Variation of Ocelli Size Between Male and Female Bees in Species of Different Sociality. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0v065150>
6. Wong-Lau, J., Klauke, H., Kaur, H., Alexander, N., Bang, J., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Big-Bee: Hair Recognition and Quantification. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0fb1n3pw>
7. Miller, J. T, & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Environmental Trends in the Distribution of California Bee Species. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/36w6x8pp>
8. Thrift, C. N, & Seltmann, K. C. (2021). Identifying island-mainland bee populations with wings. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4h46m0ws>
9. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Ostwald MM, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E. Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. (July 3-8, 2022). International Union for the Study of Social Insects (IUSSI), San Diego, CA.
10. SEMC will present the Big-Bee initiative at the XIII International Union for the Study of Social Insect—Andean and Caribbean branch (Aug 14-17, 2022) <https://sites.google.com/site/iussiseccionbolivariana/>

. This meeting attracts numerous researchers from Latin America and the Caribbean. The presentation will be in Spanish.

11. Seltmann and Jorrit Poelen (GloBI) will present about Big-Bee and sharing bee trait and image data at sDevTrait II (August 8-11, 2022), Leipzig, Germany.

Websites and Data Portals:

Big-Bee project website: <http://big-bee.net>

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: <https://library.big-bee.net>

Big-Bee focused Global Biotic Interactions project page: <https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee>

iDigBio Wiki:

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN: Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization \(Big-Bee\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN:_Extending_Anthophila_research_through_image_and_trait_digitization_(Big-Bee))

Big-Bee Network GitHub Project: <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network>

YouTube (Macroscopic Solutions): <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn;>

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg>

Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza project: <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Other Publications:

1. The full proposal can be found at Seltmann, K. C. (2021). Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) proposal. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2vm761mv>
2. Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021). UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5557670>. Data publication that includes full UCSB Invertebrate Zoology Collection image corpus.
3. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2021). Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722445> on 24 Nov 2021
4. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022). Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.2.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915003> on 28 Jan 2022
5. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022). Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.3.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> on 28 Jan 2022
6. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, Taro, Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022). Big Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6950082>
7. Big-Bee publishes a quarterly report of global bee interactions indexed by GloBI that includes additional data curation such as the removal of duplicate records. This publication includes interactions from museum specimens, journal publications, and observations in both comma and tab-delimited formats.

Other Products (Non-scholarly Articles):

1. Shelly Leachman (2021). Creating a Buzz. UCSB Current. Retrieved from <https://www.news.ucsb.edu/2021/020448/creating-buzz> on 27 Oct 2021.
2. Tara Duggan. (2021). To help fight the loss of bees, the California Academy of Sciences to share a 180,000-strong collection online. San Francisco Chronicle. Retrieved from <https://www.sfchronicle.com/climate/article/To-help-fight-loss-of-bees-California-Academy-of-16570034.php> on 2 Nov 2021.
3. Matt Kettmann. Bee Happy. UC Santa Barbara Magazine Retrieved from <https://magazine.ucsb.edu/spring-summer-2022/bee-happy> on July 25, 2022.

Participants

13 institutions are funded by the Big-Bee project (Table 5). Lead participants and institution codes are listed below from each institution. A total of 97 people worked on the Big-Bee project including PIs, collection

managers, students, volunteers, technicians, and postdoctoral scholars (Table 6). **41** undergraduate students received some financial compensation for the project and **16** students received course credit. **4** graduate students and **2** postdoctoral scholars contributed to the project.

Institution	Institution Code	Participant	Institution affiliation
Arizona State University	ASUHIC	Nico Franz	School of Life Sciences, Hasbrouck Insect Collection
		Ed Gilbert	School of Life Sciences
		Sangmi Lee	Hasbrouck Insect Collection
California Academy of Sciences	CAS	Chris Grinter	California Academy of Sciences, Entomology
Florida State Collection of Arthropods	FSCA	Elijah Talamas	Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Division of Plant Industry
Harvard University	MCZ	Naomi Pierce	Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Museum of Comparative Zoology
		Crystal Maier	Museum of Comparative Zoology, Entomology
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County	LACM	Brian Brown	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
		Giar-Ann Kung	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
San Diego Natural History Museum	SDMC	Pamela Horsley	San Diego Natural History Museum, Entomology
University of California-Berkeley	EMEC	Neil Tsutsui	Department of Environmental Science, Policy and Management
		Peter Oboyski	Essig Museum of Entomology
University of California, Santa Barbara	UCSB	Katja C Seltmann	Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, Earth Research Institute
University of Colorado, Boulder	UCMC	Adrian Carper	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
		Virginia Scott	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
University of Kansas	SEMC	Michael Engel	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute

		Victor Gonzalez-Betancourt	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology	UMMZI	L. Lacey Knowles	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
		Taro Eldredge	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
University of Nevada, Reno	UNR	Julie Allen	Department of Biology
University of New Hampshire	UNHC	Istvan Miko	Donald S. Chandler Entomological Collection

Table 5: List of project PIs and lead participants at each Big-Bee funded institution.

	UNHC	UMMZI	UCSB	FSCA	UNR	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHC	MCZ	Total
Undergraduate students hired (i.e., paid)	3	2	10	0	0	2	1	7	1	6	0	3	6	41
Undergraduate students working for course credit	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	3	0	16
Undergraduate student volunteers	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	5
Non-student volunteers	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	5
Graduate students	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4
Non-student staff	1	0	2	3	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	1	3	21
Total number of people	6	6	25	3	3	4	2	9	5	12	4	9	9	97

Table 6: Number of people involved in Big-Bee

Partner Organizations

- Notes from Nature
- US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN
- iDigBio
- Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)
- Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)
- USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab
- Macroscopic Solutions, LLC

Other Collaborators

Erika Tucker - Terrestrial Parasite Tracker Digitization Taxonomy Manager, Milwaukee Public Museum; Research Associate, Biodiversity Outreach Network (BON)

Hollis Woodard - Assistant Professor, University of California - Riverside; PI USDA US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN (<https://www.usnativebees.com>)

Elizabeth Hill - Agricultural Research Service, US Department of Agriculture
Andrew Johnson - Invertebrate Collections Manager - NEON Biorepository, Arizona State University, Symbiota Support Hub

Andrew Johnson - ASU, Neon Biorepository, Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Katie Pearson - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); CAP TCN

Lindsay Walker - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Thomas van de Kamp - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Laboratory for Applications of Synchrotron Radiation

Robert Guralnick - Curator of Biodiversity Informatics, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, iDigBio, Notes from Nature

Bob Blinn - Collection Manager, North Carolina State University Insect Museum

Dylan Valle Rogers - Collaborator, Essig Museum of Entomology

José Augusto Salim - Center on Biodiversity and Computing (www.biocomp.org.br), Universidade de São Paulo

Sophie Cardinal - Canadian National Collection

Keng-Lou James Hung - Assistant Professor of Biology, Oklahoma Biological Survey

Steve Baskauf - Data Science and Data Curation Specialist, Jean & Alexander Heard Libraries, Vanderbilt University; Convener of the TDWG Audubon Core Views Controlled Vocabularies Task Group (<https://github.com/tdwg/ac/blob/master/views/README.md>)

Impacts

What is the impact on the development of the principal discipline(s) of the project?

Although still in early development, Big-Bee is demonstrating a distributed system of sharing image and specimen records using linked data using hash technology. The data sharing methodology could facilitate dataset sharing that more accurately keeps track of data provenance. Records and images from the Bee Library are also shared as citable data publications through the Internet Archive and Zenodo. These published archives have a digital identifier (DOI) and an identifier that verifiably identifies the archive content (hash). The archives include metadata describing the origin of the specimen records and images, and the records and images themselves. An example of an early published image corpus is available at:

Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021). UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5557670><https://archive.org/details/preston-ucsb-izchash://sha256/d5eb492d3e0304afadcc85f968de1e23042479ad670a5819cee00f2c2c277f36>

Big-Bee is also actively participating in the US Bee Monitoring Research Coordination Network. The impact of our involvement helps bring a specimen-based perspective to ecological research including the importance of voucher specimens and collections. In addition, PI Seltmann and collaborators Elizabeth Hill, Hollis Woodard,

and Erika Tucker are developing a two-day workshop on biodiversity data for Bee Monitoring Network participants. This workshop has been identified as the first, much-needed data boot camp for over 100 participants that come from state and federal agencies (i.e., USDA, USGS), universities, non-profits, and many other groups interested in improving the US bee monitoring programs.

Big-Bee digitization is noticeably increasing and facilitating new bee-related research. Listed here are a few examples of Big-Bee's impact.

- UCSB Seltmann mentored Zoe Wood who received a Big-Bee related NSF GRFP. Zoe will be attending UC Davis in the fall to work with Dr. Emily Meineke.
- UCSB undergraduate student, JT Miller, will be going to Dr. Pam Soltis lab this summer for an iDigBio research internship. JT's research involves the spatial distribution of bees in California.
- Big-Bee images are now part of a research project looking at bee visual acuity with UCSB faculty Todd Oakley and Eleanor Caves (UCSB). This collaboration is aimed at testing the use of images to predict the differences in vision between bee species or within a single species.
- The Florida State Collection of Arthropods hosted two visitors who specialize in bees. Dr. Robert Pemberton and Dr. David Roubik. Dr. Pemberton was interested in *Euglossa* bees in Florida, so FSCA prioritized data capture from *Euglossa viridissima* and *E. dilemma* to make these available. They have also been in communication with Dr. Elif Kardas, curator of an insect collection in Puerto Rico, who intends to visit FSCA later this year to capture label data and images of Puerto Rican bees, which will be added to the bee library.
- UCMC trained two museum graduate assistants in 2D and 3D imaging as part of their research and for an *Emerging Museum Technologies* course.
- UCMC also trained a Ph.D. student in the Dept of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology in 2D imaging, as part of her descriptions of two gynandromorphic bee specimens previously undocumented.

What is the impact on other disciplines?

Big-Bee is actively seeking partners for developing artificial intelligence and improved 3D modeling applications using Big-Bee images. Seltmann mentored students from UCSB Statistics and Applied Probability Department for a Data Science Capstone. This capstone focused on methods for describing bee hairiness, extraction of EXIF data from images, and reading barcodes from images. This is in collaboration with the <https://centralcoastdatascience.org> NSF-supported project.

Big-Bee is promoting the sharing of images under Creative Commons 0/Public Domain licenses, which already has received attention from MediaWiki and computer vision bee identification initiatives (Brian Spiesman - <https://beemachine.ai>; Automated Wildlife Monitoring - <https://automated-wildlife-cig.github.io>) that are actively searching for open images of bees. Open access to images is also an important impact in the realm of technology transfer.

Big-Bee efforts in image sharing and data reporting led to the improvement of existing open tools like Preston, Nomer, and Elton (see <https://jhpoelen.nl> for more info) to the benefit of other publicly funded projects such as "*Intelligently predicting viral spillover risks from bats and other wild mammals*" (NIH R21 Grant 1R21AI164268-01 - <https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/10289637>), "*Towards the Web of Biodiversity Knowledge: Understanding Data Connectedness to Improve Identifier Practices*" (NSF OAC 1839201 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1839201), "*Digitizing collections to trace parasite-host associations and predict the spread of vector-borne disease - Parasite Tracker TCN*" (NSF DBI:1901932 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1901932).

What is the impact on the development of human resources?

97 people were part of this project in the first year. 52% of the Big-Bee participants are gender minorities in science and engineering (Women, Trans people, etc.) and 21% are people of color/ racial and ethnic minority groups in science and engineering (Black or African American, Hispanic, Indigenous).

In our proposal, we expressed a commitment to recruiting participants from underserved communities using existing programs already found at the collaborating institutions. To track these metrics, Big-Bee created a first draft DEI survey for our annual report. The survey is based on a survey used for the CAP TCN that includes groups defined as underrepresented in Science and Engineering

(<https://www.nsf.gov/statistics/2017/nsf17310/digest/introduction>). LACM Big-Bee participants updated the survey to improve the language to be more inclusive.

ASU Hosted an Entomology week for the Justice, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (JEDI) summer research scholars program. They demonstrated and taught collections management, imaging, and digitization activities used for Big-Bee with the scholars.

UCSB awarded two paid, full-time internships for students identified by the UCSB Office of Education Partnerships, Smithsonian Scholars program. The interns are participating in imaging bees and working with Notes from Nature. The Office of Education Partnerships mission is to increase college-going rates for students who are low-income and/or will be the first in their families to pursue higher education.

What is the impact on teaching and education experiences?

Undergraduate students make up a large proportion of the workforce in university collections. Big-Bee has already demonstrated a commitment to training the next generation of collection managers and biodiversity researchers about the use and importance of natural history collections. Big-Bee institutions hired **41** undergraduate students, **16** participated for course credit and **5** as volunteers. The students gave **3** oral presentations about Big-Bee and **5** posters.

UMMZI is developing a flexible teaching module for upper-level high school and lower-level undergraduate courses using biodiversity data repositories (i.e., iDigBio, GBIF). The module will be designed to explore the effects of climate change in host and species range size using available longitudinal museum data. A beta version will be shared with the Big-Bee group for comments and will be made publicly available.

PI Seltmann taught a quarter-long course on Museum and Collection Management (ENVS/EEMB 96) where 12 students participated in transcribing data, curating specimens, and discussions about bee and museum specimens. LACM Giar-Ann Kung participated by providing data for students and attended in person and remotely during classes.

UCMC Adrian Carper has also included slides of the project in two guest lectures, Advanced Seminar: *Emerging Technologies in Museum Studies*. University of Colorado-Boulder (MUSM 6110) and *Beeography*, Geography and Environmental Sciences, University of Colorado-Denver (GEOG 5500).

What is the impact on physical resources that form infrastructure?

The increased communication between bee collections created a forum for sharing information beyond just the Big-Bee project and about infrastructure. This has led directly to exchanges of physical resources including cabinets/drawers from LACM given to UCSB. CAS PI Grinter visited the Essig collection and took notes from PI Oboyski's digitization setup and borrowed equipment. This exchange of equipment and knowledge provided the resources for a second photo station at CAS. In another example, UMMZI reviewed the SEMC's Big-Bee digitization setup for ideas and inspiration to create a new digitization system at UMMZI.

UCMC and other collections also noted that the imaging stations have also been used by other researchers within the museum, in other departments, and from around the world. Thus, the Macropod Pro system and other imaging infrastructure gained during this project is impacting research outside the Big-Bee project.

- A UCMC Ph.D. student in the Dept of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, used their new tablet imaging station to calculate butterfly wing morphometrics and explore how secondary metabolite sequestration and temperature impact wing morphology and flight performance.
- UCMC also hosted visiting faculty from the Instituto Multidisciplinario de Biología Vegetal (CONICET-UNC, Argentina) who has been 2D imaging *Solanum* spp. seeds for comparative paleontological studies.

What is the impact on institutional resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on information resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on technology transfer?

Big-Bee has benefited greatly from prior technological developments of other TCNs. Our portal is managed by the Symbiota Support Hub (ASU & iDigBio), which hosts the majority of the Symbiota portals at this time. Because of the HUB experience, the Big-Bee Library was launched successfully in the first few months of the project. We are building off of the trait module started from the CAP TCN and the interactions with Global Biotic Interactions originally initiated by the Tri-Tropic TCN and further developed during the Parasite Tracker TCN. Symbiota users also have access to developments and innovations during the Big-Bee project through our GitHub repository.

Big-Bee drove the development of the Macropod 3D modeling system through user testing that led to innovations in this technology. These innovations improved the product for all future users.

Big-Bee published the world catalog of bees from DiscoverLife on Zenodo in comma and tab-delimited formats. Doing so allowed for this important catalog to be incorporated into Global Names, nomer, and other taxon name resolution services for the first time. Incorporation into Global Names ensured the bee catalog is also available to researchers through several R packages, including the *taxize* package. The DiscoverLife catalog of bee names is considered the most up-to-date of all available bee name lists, thus improving access to all researchers and projects needing bee names.

What is the impact on society beyond science and technology?

One of the largest impacts of the project is our commitment to increasing awareness about bees and other insects in our communities. This comes through outreach events of all kinds, including support for Xerxes Society conservation initiatives such as the Bee Campus program, pollinator gardens, or bug-themed museum events. A total of **4367** people attended Big-Bee related events.

- UCMC - A. Carper (PI) has included the project in three outreach events to foster interest in our future *Notes from Nature* expeditions:
 - CU Boulder Mountain Research Station 100th Anniversary Seminar Series (6/21/2022): *Colorado's Wild Bees Expanding the Conservation Impacts of Pollinator Research*
 - CU Conference on World Affairs Panel (4/8/2022): *Silent Farm: Saving our Birds, Bees, Frogs, and Ourselves*
 - People & Pollinators Action Network Webinar (4/7/2022): *Challenges in Conserving Colorado's Native Bees*
- CAS - Chris Grinter led behind the scenes collection tours with a focus on bees and pollinators for a combined 42 people during the reporting period.
- CAS - Grinter lead a class tour focused on pollinators for U San Francisco and Dr Sevan Suni.
- CAS - Dylan Bergersen (and other departmental staff) participated in Bug themed nightlife at the Cal Academy on Thursday, June 2nd titled "Buggin Out" <https://www.calacademy.org/nightlife/nightlife-buggin-out> Drawers of bees were included with specimens for live tabling event.
- EMEC - Ongoing Pollinator Garden project as part of a Xerxes Society Bee Campus. Students plant and manage native California plants in a demonstration garden on the UC Berkeley campus and collect qualitative and quantitative data on flower-visiting insects.
- UCSB - was recognized officially as a Xerxes Society Bee Campus this year.
- EMEC - Entomology lecture and field experience for the California Naturalist certification course at UC Santa Cruz. This ten-week course exposes students to California ecosystems, flora, and fauna. The entomology section focuses on the diversity and role of insects, including as vital pollinators for native and agricultural plants.
- EMEC - Santa Cruz Natural History Museum member hike. Led a hike for SCNHM members focusing on native insects, particularly pollinators, and their interactions with plants and other organisms.
- EMEC - Annual Sonoma Bee Count. This all-day event introduces local residents to California's native bees and the flower resources they depend on through group discussions and hands-on data collection activities. Records from the day's surveys will be added to the Big-Bee TCN data set.
- EMEC - Museum tours including NSF-funded Research Experience for Undergraduate (REU) students; Local 4H chapter; and UC Berkeley class "Ecology and Society."

What percentage of the award's budget was spent in a foreign country?

Nothing to report.

Changes/Problems

We have nothing to report for changes in approach, expenditure impact, care of human subjects, care of vertebrate animals, or changes in the use of biohazards.

Actual or Anticipated problems or delays and actions or plans to resolve them:

We anticipated problems due to the COVID-19 pandemic, but all major delays were avoided. Participants can access their collections and also have staff/students in the collections. It was reported that hiring new staff took longer than expected at this time. There were some supply chain issues, especially with purchasing new computer equipment.

We anticipated much larger problems with the supply chain for our imaging equipment, but Macroscopic Solutions pre-emptively ordered inventories 1 year in advance in preparation for Big-Bee because of anticipated supply chain problems. Despite ordering in advance, critical lens and flash units were not delivered even 1.5 years after the order had been placed. To prevent project delays, Macroscopic Solutions sourced used or ancillary equipment for all participating Big-Bee members to use until the new and warranted equipment arrived.